

DEMAND RESPONSE STRATEGY FOR OPTIMAL FORMULATION OF FLEXIBILITY SERVICES

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Abstract

Demand Response (DR) gains widespread support in the EU, as reflected in regulatory initiatives that encourage its market uptake and in the numerous pilot deployments that investigate its impact and acceptance. DR facilitates the cost-efficient integration of renewable energy sources and can contribute on reduced CO₂ emissions. Also, it is beneficial for the electricity users, offering them financial incentives for reshaping their electricity consumption pattern. A key player in the realization of DR is the DR Aggregator. To accomplish its business objectives, this stakeholder needs ICT tools that support forecasting of the amount and flexibility of consumption, optimal planning of the flexibility of aggregated assets, baseline calculation and participation verification for settlement and billing purposes, and strategic positioning of the aggregated flexibility in the markets. Much of the innovation of these tools is focused on the components that analyze the flexibility portfolio and dynamically calculate proper incentives that ensure profitability for the DR Aggregator. This paper presents our approach for a Demand Response Management System and details the devised aggregated flexibility forecasting algorithms. It also presents a policy for optimal allocation of load curtailment/enhancement targets to DR programs and enrolled customers and analyses the rationale behind this policy.

1 Introduction

Europe's energy landscape is experiencing profound change as increasing amounts of Renewable Energy Sources (RES) and other variable generation resources displace conventional forms of generation [1]. This development goes hand-in-hand with an expanding share of power production that takes place at the distribution level. However, variations in wind and solar generation result in a distribution system that is more complex to plan, to control and to balance. The pattern of generation moves away from primarily dispatchable to variable, distributed generation and the share of distributed resources increases significantly. At the same time, the energy consumer becomes also an energy provider (prosumer) as the energy from

distributed micro-generation units is fed back to the power grid.

The rising share of distributed generation in the system results in lower predictability for the electricity markets and for the grid operation, and implies the need for increased flexibility to cope with this volatility. Flexibility can help to avoid inefficiency in the markets and allay the concerns that the future mix of generation capacity may not meet demand at optimal costs [2]. For these reasons it is strongly believed that initiatives that facilitate flexibility along with consumer engagement and empowerment will replace or at least defer traditional investments on the grid.

When discussion comes to enablers of the consumer engagement and empowerment, Demand Response (DR) is a potential game changing technology, which can alter completely the fundamentals of the energy industry. DR is linked to changes made by end users in terms of their regular energy consumption. It is formed around incentives tailored to shape energy load profiles and serves as a tool to assist the grid operation when reliability is compromised.

There are two flavours of DR: explicit and implicit [3]. In explicit DR schemes (also called "incentive-based") consumers receive direct payments to change their consumption upon request (i.e., consuming more or less), which is typically triggered by activation of balancing services, differences in electricity prices or a constraint on the network. Consumers can earn from their flexibility in electricity consumption individually or by contracting with an aggregator. The latter can either be an independent DR Aggregator or the customer's Energy Retailer. Implicit DR (also called "price-based") refers to the cases in which consumers are exposed to time-varying electricity prices or time-varying network tariffs (or both) that partly reflect the value or cost of electricity and/or transportation in different time periods and react to those price differences depending on their own preferences and constraints.

To accomplish their business objectives around DR, the DR service providers need ICT tools that support forecasting of the amount and flexibility of consumption, optimal planning of the flexibility of aggregated assets, baseline calculation and participation verification for settlement and billing purposes, and strategic positioning of the aggregated flexibility in the

markets. Much of the innovation of these tools is focused on the components that analyse the flexibility portfolio and dynamically calculate proper incentives that ensure profitability for the DR Aggregator.

The research work around this topic is not negligible. ADDRESS [4], a large-scale Integrated Project co-funded by the European Commission under the 7th Framework Programme, is reference project on tools for demand aggregation and optimization. In [5] the authors make use of an autoregressive integrated moving average method for forecasting loads and energy market prices, with the aim to devise bidding strategy for the DR Aggregators. In [6] the authors present a policy for devising incentives for DR programs that take into account the customers' behaviour with respect to electricity price change and his/her behaviour against variation of incentive. Finally, authors in [7] present an optimization model to adjust the hourly load level of a given consumer in response to hourly electricity prices. The objective of the model is to maximize the utility of the consumer subject to a minimum daily energy-consumption level, maximum and minimum hourly load levels, and ramping limits on such load levels.

In this paper we present our approach for a Demand Response Management System and details of the devised aggregated flexibility forecasting algorithms. We also present a policy for optimal allocation of load shaping targets to DR programs and enrolled customers and we analyse the rationale behind this policy.

2 Demand Response Concepts

2.1 Flexibility Services & Demand Response

On an individual level flexibility is the modification of generation injection and/or consumption patterns in reaction to an external signal (price signal or activation) in order to provide a service within the energy system [8]. Amount of power modulation, duration, rate of change, response time, and location are some of the parameters used to shape flexibility, which may be based on a diverse set of resources such as demand response, energy generation and energy storage. In turn, the level of certainty in the management of these assets affects the reliability of a flexibility service. Particularly demand response may encompass non trivial uncertainty, especially for price based DR programs or when non-compliance is not penalized. This can lead to situations where more resources are activated for ensuring the required flexibility, which results in the increment of the overall cost of the service. With this in mind, a need for reducing the uncertainty of the DR-based flexibility services while optimizing its reliability and cost arises. Automated DR can tackle this matter, requires however a significant investment in infrastructure on the client's side. In this scheme, DR resources are modelled by an expected power shed volume (or range with upper and lower bounds) and equivalent cost, as well as a degree of reliability which

expresses the risk for achieving it. In our study we consider also non-automated DR programs.

2.2 Demand Response Management System

A Demand Response Management System (DRMS) enables the aggregation and management of flexibility by leveraging an abundance of DR programs and resources. Provided flexibility can cover both economical (energy/cost efficiency) and technical (grid services) perspectives of the electricity market. Further to supporting the basic operations of scheduling and dispatching DR events, a DRMS must also include a mechanism for optimal selection of DR programs and participants for different/multiple strategies, aiming ultimately at reliable and cost effective flexibility. Such a system can be utilized by an Aggregator to aggregate, plan and submit flexibility bids to the electricity markets, as well as the activation of flexibility services. Furthermore, it can be utilized by a System Operator (e.g. DSO) as a means of activating flexibility for grid support, in case the market structure permits such policies.

Figure 1 DRMS Architecture

Figure 1 provides an overview of the architectural design of the DRMS developed in the context of SmarterEMC2 [9]. The system is comprised of the following components:

- *Flexibility Manager*: Responsible for forecasting demand response capacity, filtering programs and resources according to the calculated flexibility or flexibility requests, as well as placing market bids;
- *DR Engine*: Implements the DR Logic of the system; runs the algorithms for selecting the mix of programs / participants and manages the DR events' lifecycle;
- *DR Coms*: Handles demand response related communications (registration, notification, availability, reports etc) of the system with DR resources. The component handles inter-DRMS interactions as well.

- *GUI*: Manages the web interface for administrating programs, participants, events and DR resources;
- *Monitoring*: Monitors system's health, notification and feedback of DR events, and calculates measurement and verification reports;
- *Analytics Engine*, provides energy forecasts and performance metrics;
- *Database*: Handles database connections, acting as an interface for storing and retrieving data to/from the data repository.

The DRMS provides *flexibility services* to diverse flexibility consumers such as:

- *Virtual Power Plants (VPPs)*, i.e. aggregations of DERs, flexible loads and DR resources not necessarily located in the same region;
- *Distribution System Operators (DSOs)*, by exchanging flexibility information with their Distribution Management System (DMS);
- *Market Operators*, for submitting market bids and receiving activation schedules;

An interface with the *Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI)* provides energy measurements of the DR resources, whilst an interface with *Customer Energy Management Systems (CEMS)*, is dedicated to exchanging DR information (events, reports etc.) with the customer's premises equipment. There is also an *inter-DRMS* interface for DR signals exchange among different Demand Response Management Systems, enabling a multi-layered hierarchy.

2.3 DR policy

The system supports both incentive-based and price-based programs and different cost models: fixed monthly payments, remuneration per kWh reduced, different price tiers etc. as well as different baseline calculation methods.

More specifically, the following programs are supported:

- *Critical Peak Pricing (CPP)*: participants are offered discounted prices during non-peak hours, whilst during critical situations they receive a higher price, with an aim to decrease demand;
- *Base Interruptible Program (BIP)*: Participants in this program receive a monthly bill credit for a (potential) load reduction at a predetermined level. Failure to comply results into penalty charges.
- *Fast DR Dispatch*: Participants provide pre-committed loads that are being used in "real-time" DR events (resources are typically dispatched in less than 10 minutes after the notification).
- *Capacity Bidding DR Program*: an Aggregator-managed program which allows participation in retail and wholesale markets by offering load

reductions at a price or by notifying how much load can be curtailed for a given price. The Aggregator manages its DR resources by making use of various types of programs;

The DRMS supports various DR policies, individually or combined, with the aim to accomplish the different objectives of the business entity that makes use of it:

- *Cost Minimization*: Minimizes the cost of delivering flexibility based on the cost of each DR program;
- *Reliability Maximization*: Maximizes the reliability of delivered flexibility based on a reliability index;
- *Efficiency of participation*: Prioritizes the selection of the most efficient consumers, in terms of delivering the requested flexibility;
- *Fairness of participation*: Provides equal opportunities to consumers with fewer participations in past DR events, even if efficiency is limited.

3 Optimization Problem

The problem we aim to solve is to optimally allocate flexibility i.e. load shaping targets to consumers, through DR events, with the objective to fulfil the DR policies and satisfy the consumers' constraints (i.e. availability) and programs' restrictions (lower-upper limits, start/end time, min/max duration of event). In its current version, the algorithm focuses on demand reduction capacity; however, demand increase will be incorporated in future versions of the algorithm.

Figure 2 depicts a decomposition of the problem in a flow of processes performed by the system in order to provide an optimal solution. The series of processes, which is triggered either by a flexibility request or by a bid formulation request, is analyzed in the following subparagraphs.

3.1 Customer Segmentation

This periodical process segments the customer pool, based on their characteristics, in several clusters. Profiling characteristics used for the classification of customers include: DR program enrolled, customer type, location, baseline calculation method, contractual power, monthly energy consumption, demand elasticity (for price based programs). Aggregating multiple customer into a single "virtual customer", representative of the cluster, reduces the number of variables in the optimization problem and results in a simplified and less greedy computational problem.

Figure 2 Flexibility allocation algorithm

Furthermore, the impact of load consumption prediction errors for the “virtual customer” is reduced compared to that of individual customers.

3.2 Filtering

This process is run upon receiving an activation request for a flexibility service, with the aim to filter available DR programs and identify the most suitable one according to the request’s details and the programs restrictions (i.e. call window, time period of the year, min. advance notification and min. event duration).

3.3 Capacity Forecasting

This process estimates the available flexibility (DR capacity) of each cluster, based on its profile characteristics, its members’ state and its load consumption forecast.

Load consumption forecasting (short-term) is used as a baseline for assessing participation in DR events as well as estimating available flexibility. Several models exist in the literature for calculating the consumer’s baseline, which can be loosely categorized in averaging methods and regression methods [10]. Each method provides a different balance of accuracy, simplicity and integrity, whilst different results can be obtained according to the characteristics of the customer. Baseline calculation is an important aspect of providing an effective service; however a detailed analysis is out of scope of this paper. In brief, different methods are supported by our DRMS, which leverage historical consumption and weather information data, in order to produce valid results and predict the actual performance of heterogeneous types of customers.

Estimating the available capacity for incentive-based programs can be achieved with a straightforward approach. In particular, for programs with contracted amount of power shed, the available capacity is calculated by comparing the load consumption forecast to the contracted amount and the firm service level (or base load) of the participant. Likewise, for incentive based programs with contracted reduction to the firm service level, this capacity is calculated by comparing the load consumption forecast to the firm service level.

For price based programs the task is more devious. The available capacity can be estimated using elasticity [11], demand (D) and energy prices (π), following the elasticity definition:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{\frac{\Delta D}{D}}{\frac{\Delta \pi}{\pi}}, (1)$$

Elasticity can be estimated by averaging DR event historical data of the participant, using the baseline ($b_{c,t}$) as D, the achieved reduction $\Delta D_{c,t}$ and the relevant prices of the event ($\pi'_{c,t}$) and before ($\pi_{c,t}$) for $\Delta \pi$ and π , respectively. Hence, available flexibility of cluster c, at time interval t, can be approximated by the following formula:

$$\Delta D_{c,t} = \frac{\bar{\varepsilon}_{c,t} \times (\pi'_{c,t} - \pi_{c,t}) \times b_{c,t}}{\pi_{c,t}}, (2)$$

For participants with no available data, default elasticity values or the average elasticity of the cluster can be used.

Upon calculating the time series of the available capacity (dq_i areas) for each customer cluster (taking into account the availability of the population of the cluster), the final available flexibility is calculated and a set combinations of available load shedding is formulated, which comply with the constraints of min initiation / max termination time and min / max duration of the DR event are satisfied as depicted in Figure 3.

Figure 3 Capacity Forecasting Conceptual Diagram

3.4 Planning

Planning process uses the output of capacity forecasting, for solving the optimization problem of allocating load shading targets to customers' clusters, for planning DR events or preparing flexibility offers to be submitted to the market. The process takes into account a cost index and a reliability index per customers' cluster.

The cost index (€/kwh) comprises an indication of the cost of a DR program. It is calculated by averaging the total cost with the delivered flexibility by each program. This approach is dictated by the difficulty in modelling the different types of programs and the various parts that compose the cost of each program (e.g. initial equipment cost, marketing costs, monthly capacity remuneration, penalties), as well as the difficulty in comparing event activation costs among price and incentive based programs.

The reliability index (%) indicates the probability of a customers' cluster ignoring DR signals, thus providing less flexibility than expected. For the calculation of the reliability index historical data of consumption and the results of the participation verification process are used for each customer cluster.

The objective function of the system is the minimization of the cost of delivering the flexibility, in case of a service request, or the optimal formulation of a market bid. It is expressed by the equations (3) and (4), respectively:

$$\min \left[\sum_{t \in T, c \in N_c} C_{c,t} \times f_{c,t} \right] \quad (3)$$

$$\max \left[\sum_{t \in T} \left(\pi_t \times F_t - \sum_{c \in N_c} C_{c,t} \times f_{c,t} \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

where,

- $C_{c,t}$: Cost of activating cluster c at time interval t ;
- $f_{c,t}$: Offered flexibility by cluster c at time interval t ;
- F_t : Aggregated flexibility at time interval t ;
- π_t : price forecast at time interval t ;
- T : Time period of flexibility;
- N_c : Set of participating clusters.

The following constraints apply:

$$\sum_{c \in N_c} f_{c,t} \geq F_t, \forall t \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{\sum_{c \in N_c} f_{c,t} \times r_{c,t}}{F_t} \geq \rho, \forall t \quad (6)$$

where $r_{c,t}$ is the reliability index of cluster at time interval t and parameter ρ is a reliability constraint that is defined according to the DR policy of the system. In the case of market bid formulation, the equality part of equation (5) applies.

The optimization problem can be solved as a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP) problem. The set of forecasted capacity values and the constraints of equations (5) and (6) will govern the selection of variable $f_{c,t}$ and the definition of the target allocated to each cluster. For each participating cluster a DR event will be issued during Dispatch process, which will define which cluster's members to notify.

3.5 Dispatch

During this process candidate participants from each customer cluster are identified, selected and eventually notified with appropriate DR events. The selection process consists of a ranking mechanism where each cluster member is ranked according to participation fairness and efficiency indicators. The selection methodology is based on the work described in[10].

Participation fairness indicator p_i is calculated with the following formula, where 'TotalSuccessfulRequests' is the number of positive response of consumer i of cluster c to the allocated shed (calculated either through opt-out response or participation verification after event):

$$p_i = 1 - \frac{\text{TotalSuccessfulRequests}_i}{\max(\text{TotalSuccessfulRequests}_c)}, \quad (7)$$

Efficiency indicator (e_i) is calculated with the following formula, where 'PositiveOpts' is the percentage of positive answers from the client and 'Avg(Efficiency)' is the average shed performed by the client in previous events:

$$e_i = \text{PositiveOpts}_i \times \text{Avg}(\text{Efficiency})_i, \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Efficiency} = \frac{\text{CurrentShed}}{\text{ExpectedShed}}, \quad (9)$$

The ranking of participants is performed according to the following indicator:

$$r_i = w \times f_i + (1 - w) \times e_i, \quad (10)$$

where w is a weight factor. Weight factor 1 signifies that fairness maximization policy is utilized, whilst weight factor 0 signifies that efficiency maximization policy is utilized.

During the notification process the system checks and complies with any notification restrictions of the program or the participant (i.e. min advance notification). Communications with DR participant are performed according to the OpenADR 2.0 standard b profile [13], which provides an information and communication model for Demand Response and defines, among other, a notification and feedback event mechanism.

3.6 Feedback Assessment

This process monitors and evaluates the outcome (opt in/out) of the DR events' dispatch process as well as the results of participation upon events' completion. During

dispatch, it aggregates and provides feedback to the planning process, in order to proceed with any necessary supplementary planning and dispatch of DR events. Upon completion of an event, the participants' performance is evaluated by using the forecasted flexibility information (baseline) and the actual energy measurements, as imported from the AMI.

4 Conclusions and Next Steps

The paper describes our approach in designing a DRMS and the algorithms for managing DR resources with the aim to optimize the provision of flexibility services. The presented approach covers the full chain from forecasting the available flexibility to formulating competitive market bids as well as planning and dispatching available resources. Further extensions could focus on modelling load enhancements apart from shedding as well as modelling other types of resources in the customers' premises (e.g. storage), fine-tuning the capacity forecasting of price-based programs, and enriching the planning process with the capability to schedule more than one events per cluster. The herein presented DRMS will be tested in real life conditions in a residential DR pilot in Greece and in a commercial and industrial DR pilot in Turkey. The pilots' scenarios are focused on the demonstration of flexibility services provided to the DSO, as well as on the formulation of flexibility offers in a simulated energy market. These pilots will set the basis for validating the proposed technology and algorithmic approach and assessing its impact in real life conditions.

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